

Beyond Bureaucracy: BLU Business Units

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ABSTRACT

This paper advances a conceptual framework that examines how entrepreneurial mindset (EM) and AI readiness interact to shape business model innovation (BMI) and financial performance (FP) within Indonesia's profit-oriented Public Service Agency (BLU) business units. As hybrid organizations, BLU business units must simultaneously fulfill their public service mandate and generate revenue, creating a unique context that demands a stronger theoretical grounding. The framework draws on New Public Management (NPM) principles and the Dynamic Capabilities (DC) perspective to argue that an entrepreneurial mindset stimulates BMI both directly and indirectly through enhanced AI readiness. In turn, BMI is positioned as a driver of financial performance and organizational sustainability. By integrating insights from entrepreneurship, digital transformation, and public sector innovation, this study contributes conceptually to the literature on hybrid public-commercial entities. It establishes a foundation for subsequent empirical validation.

1. Introduction

Public value represents the societal impact and mission-driven outcomes of government action (Witesman, 2021). It emerges when public sector actors collaborate across boundaries and co-create markets to address complex challenges (Mazzucato and Ryan-Collins, 2022). Public Service Agencies (PSAs), as primary providers of essential services such as healthcare and education, play a central role in this process (Noordegraaf, 2018). However, they increasingly face fiscal constraints, heightened performance expectations, and pressures to innovate, often leading to the adoption of private-sector practices (Breznitz et al., 2018; Buendía-Carrillo et al., 2025).

The Indonesian Public Service Agency model, Badan Layanan Umum (BLU), embodies New Public Management (NPM) principles, which rely on contracts, incentives, and market mechanisms to enhance efficiency and service quality (Dunleavy and Hood, 1994). By granting financial autonomy and managerial discretion, BLUs are expected to be more responsive and innovative (van Huis, 2020; Sześciło, 2022). However, this autonomy gives rise to the "autonomy-control paradox," as greater independence must be balanced with regulatory coherence and accountability (Verhoest et al., 2004). To sustain service delivery and optimize resources, the Ministry of Finance Regulation No. 129/2020 (amended by No. 202/2022) permits BLUs to establish revenue-generating business units. Their sustainability, however, is shaped by strategic alignment, capital allocation, and digital infrastructure readiness (Arrfelt et al., 2015; Queiroz et al., 2020).

As hybrid entities, business units rely on corporate entrepreneurship (CE) to sustain renewal, innovation, and competitiveness (Marques et al., 2022). Central to CE is the entrepreneurial mindset (EM)—a combination of cognitive and behavioral traits that drive opportunity recognition, risk-taking, and innovation (Kuratko et al., 2021). EM shapes entrepreneurial intentions and competencies (Handayati et al., 2020; Caputo et al., 2025), enabling the pursuit of new opportunities and supporting business model innovation (BMI), which enhances adaptability in shifting markets (Szczygiel et al., 2024; Haynie et al., 2010). Through BMI, BLU units can reconfigure value creation by leveraging technology, responding to market changes, and improving service delivery (Selvakumar et al., 2025; Teece, 2010). The diffusion of Artificial Intelligence (AI) further strengthens these dynamics, with AI readiness—defined as the organizational capacity to adopt and embed AI—emerging as a critical enabler of BMI (Holmström, 2022; Jöhnk et al., 2021). For BLUs, AI readiness goes beyond technical infrastructure to represent a strategic capability grounded in dynamic capabilities (Teece et al., 1997; Teece, 2007).

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Although entrepreneurial mindset (EM), business model innovation (BMI), and digital transformation have been widely studied in private firms, little is known about how they operate in hybrid public–commercial entities such as Indonesia’s BLU business units. In particular, the role of EM in promoting BMI, the enabling function of AI readiness, and the extent to which BMI drives financial performance under dual mandates of service and revenue remain underexplored. This paper develops a conceptual framework that integrates EM, AI readiness, BMI, and financial performance, extending corporate entrepreneurship and dynamic capabilities theory into the public sector.

The framework is novel in positioning AI readiness as both an outcome of EM and a moderator of the EM–BMI relationship, offering new insights into how digital preparedness interacts with entrepreneurial orientation to foster innovation. For BLU business units, this integration is crucial: EM sparks entrepreneurial behavior, BMI reconfigures value creation, and AI readiness ensures technological adoption and resilience. Strengthening these capacities matters because it enables BLUs to remain agile and innovative while sustaining financial performance and delivering public value amid fiscal and technological pressures.

2. Research Methodology

This paper adopts a conceptual research design aimed at theory building rather than empirical testing. The approach is grounded in a systematic review and synthesis of literature on entrepreneurial mindset (EM), business model innovation (BMI), AI readiness, and financial performance (FP), with particular attention to their relevance in hybrid public–commercial organizations such as Indonesia’s BLU business units.

The development of the framework follows established practices in conceptual research, where theoretical integration and logical reasoning are used to generate propositions. Two overarching theoretical lenses guide the framework: New Public Management (NPM), which explains the managerial and financial autonomy of BLUs, and the Dynamic Capabilities (DC) framework (Teece et al., 1997; Teece, 2007), which highlights organizational capacity to sense opportunities, seize resources, and transform operations for sustained advantage.

Drawing on these perspectives, the framework (Figure 1) positions entrepreneurial mindset (EM) as the cognitive driver of entrepreneurial behavior, AI readiness as the enabling capability that facilitates technological adoption, and business model innovation (BMI) as the strategic pathway through which entrepreneurial orientation translates into improved financial performance. The interrelationships among these constructs are expressed as propositions, offering theoretically grounded explanations that set the stage for future empirical investigation.

Figure 1: The Conceptual Framework

Source: Author (2025)

2.1. Propositions

Promotive mindsets encourage bold transformation by motivating organizations to pursue opportunities and embrace change proactively. In contrast, preventive mindsets emphasize caution and long-term stability, ensuring that innovation does not compromise organizational resilience (Sawang et al., 2024). In BLU business units, striking a balance between these two orientations is essential, as they must simultaneously fulfill revenue-generating goals and safeguard their public service mandate. Beyond individual cognition, the entrepreneurial and managerial competencies of top managers—such as strategic judgment, resource orchestration, and decision-making agility—determine how the entrepreneurial mindset translates into BMI outcomes. Relational ties with stakeholders, including policymakers,

industry partners, and beneficiaries, further shape BMI's trajectory by providing access to external knowledge, legitimacy, and collaborative opportunities (Guo et al., 2013). Collectively, these insights underscore that EM is not only an internal psychological orientation but also a leadership-driven, socially embedded capability that directly facilitates BMI in hybrid organizations such as BLUs.

Proposition 1 (P1). *Entrepreneurial mindset positively influences business model innovation.*

An entrepreneurial mindset (EM) not only drives opportunity recognition and innovation but also cultivates openness toward emerging technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI). Organizations with strong entrepreneurial orientation—characterized by innovativeness, proactiveness, and risk-taking—are more inclined to experiment with AI applications, allocate resources for digital transformation, and build the necessary cultural and structural foundations to support adoption (Dixon and Sebesta, 2025). By fostering curiosity, adaptability, and a forward-looking perspective, EM equips managers and employees to embrace AI as a tool for efficiency, real-time decision-making, and value creation (Jeremiah, 2025; Julie et al., 2024). In hybrid entities such as BLU business units, this mindset ensures that AI readiness is not viewed merely as a technical challenge but as a strategic capability aligned with organizational renewal.

Proposition 2 (P2). *Entrepreneurial mindset positively influences AI readiness.*

While an entrepreneurial mindset (EM) equips BLU business units with the cognitive and behavioral orientation to pursue innovation, its effectiveness in driving business model innovation (BMI) is amplified when organizations possess strong AI readiness. AI readiness—encompassing digital infrastructure, data capabilities, cultural openness, and strategic alignment—provides the technological and organizational foundation that enables EM to be translated into concrete innovations (Holmström, 2022). In this context, EM creates the vision and motivation for change, while AI readiness supplies the tools and capabilities necessary to operationalize that vision. For BLU units, this synergy ensures that entrepreneurial initiatives do not remain abstract but are embedded in reconfigured value-creation processes supported by AI-driven insights and efficiencies. Thus, AI readiness strengthens the pathway through which EM drives BMI, making innovation outcomes more robust and sustainable.

Proposition 3 (P3). *AI readiness strengthens the relationship between entrepreneurial mindset and business model innovation.*

Business model innovation (BMI) has been widely recognized as a driver of organizational performance by enabling firms to redesign how they create, deliver, and capture value. While prior studies highlight mediating and moderating mechanisms such as efficiency gains, organizational capabilities, and business renewal (Latifi et al., 2021; Saunila et al., 2024), evidence also shows that BMI can exert a direct positive impact on financial outcomes. By enhancing revenue streams, improving resource allocation, and aligning offerings with market demand, BMI strengthens an organization's ability to sustain profitability even in competitive or resource-constrained environments (Esau et al., 2021). For BLU business units, which must balance financial sustainability with public service obligations, BMI provides the strategic flexibility to achieve both goals simultaneously.

Proposition 4 (P4). *Business model innovation directly influences financial performance.*

2.2. Research Design

2.2.1. Population and Sample Plan

The study population comprises all BLU business units in Indonesia established under the Ministry of Finance Regulation No. 129/2020, as amended by No. 202/2022. As of 2025, 124 revenue-generating business units operate under 25 parent BLUs, consisting of 20 in the education sector (universities and polytechnics) and 5 in the healthcare sector (hospitals). These entities were chosen because they represent hybrid organizations that combine commercial logics with public service mandates, making them a relevant setting for examining the relationships among entrepreneurial mindset (EM), business model innovation (BMI), AI readiness, and financial performance.

To ensure adequate sectoral representation, a probability sampling strategy was employed. The minimum required sample size was calculated using G*Power for structural Equation modeling–partial least squares (SEM–PLS) with three predictors, yielding 77 business units ($f^2 = 0.15$, power = 0.80, $\alpha = 0.05$). Following Hair et al. (2019), a larger sample was targeted to improve model stability, minimize sampling error, and enhance the generalizability of findings across the education and healthcare sectors. Stratified random sampling was applied to proportionally capture both education- and healthcare-based business units.

2.2.2. Measurement

Four constructs were assessed:

- Entrepreneurial Mindset (EM): Measured using Caputo et al. (2025) validated scale, covering cognitive and behavioral traits, such as opportunity recognition, proactiveness, and risk-taking.
- Business Model Innovation (BMI): Assessed with Shinkle et al. (2023) Bullseye framework across 11 strategic dimensions (e.g., industry attractiveness, competitive advantage, stakeholder support, technology readiness, feasibility, and risk assumptions).
- AI Readiness: Evaluated using Holmström’s 2022 multidimensional model (technologies, activities, boundaries, goals) on a five-point readiness scale (1 = none, 5 = excellent).
- Financial Performance (FP): Based on unit financial reports (validated by the Ministry of Finance) and rated on cost structure, operating margin, and revenue contribution relative to parent BLU (1 = very weak, 5 = very strong).

All perceptual constructs (EM and BMI) were measured on a five-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree). Financial performance was assessed using both objective data (validated reports) and perceptual indicators to reduce common method bias. Construct reliability and validity were evaluated using Cronbach’s alpha, composite reliability, AVEs, and HTMT ratios, and standard method variance was assessed using Harman’s single-factor test, following Hair et al. (2019).

3. Results and Discussion

The proposed framework identifies Entrepreneurial Mindset (EM) as the cognitive and behavioral driver of innovation. AI Readiness functions both as an enabling capability and a moderator of the EM–BMI relationship, while Business Model Innovation (BMI) serves as the pathway for value reconfiguration. Financial Performance (FP) emerges as the outcome, with four propositions (P1–P4) summarizing these relationships (Table 1).

In BLU business units, the EM drives BMI through opportunity recognition, proactiveness, and calculated risk-taking. Based on desk review, university BLUs exemplify this by commercializing ethical clearance services for external users and developing digital marketplaces to extend research-based offerings. At the same time, hospitals reflect EM by expanding into aesthetic and wellness services that capture rising lifestyle-driven demand. Scaling these initiatives requires AI readiness, which provides the technological backbone for operational effectiveness and differentiation: natural language processing can potentially streamline ethical clearance reviews, while machine learning and chatbots enhance marketplace personalization and responsiveness; in wellness services, computer vision and predictive analytics enable advanced diagnostics and forecast client needs.

By integrating EM and AI readiness, BMI emerges as the mechanism through which BLUs reconfigure value creation, delivery, and capture, directly enhancing financial performance. Ethical clearance builds credibility, diversifying revenue streams, and wellness services position BLUs in growth-oriented markets. Through AI integration, BLUs increase contributions to parent BLU, ensuring financial sustainability while fulfilling their public service mandate.

4. Conclusions

This paper proposes a conceptual framework integrating entrepreneurial mindset (EM), business model innovation (BMI), and AI readiness to explain how BLU business units can improve financial performance while upholding their public service mandate. Drawing on New Public Management and Dynamic Capabilities, the framework positions EM

Table 1
Summary of the conceptual framework and propositions

Construct	Role in Framework	Dimensions	Propositions
Entrepreneurial Mindset (EM)	Cognitive and behavioral driver; initiates innovation and opportunity exploration	Opportunity recognition, proactiveness, risk-taking	P1: EM → BMI; P2: EM → AI Readiness
AI Readiness	Enabler or moderator; ensures EM translates into business model innovation	Technologies, activities, boundaries, goals	P3: AI Readiness strengthens EM → BMI
Business Model Innovation (BMI)	Strategic pathway: reconfigures value creation and delivery through EM and AI Readiness	industry attractiveness, competitive advantage, desirability, stakeholder support, technology readiness, disruption robustness, feasibility, flexibility, activity interdependencies, viability, and acceptable risks and assumptions	P4: BMI → FP
Financial Performance (FP)	Outcome of BMI reflects the sustainability of BLU units under dual mandates	cost structure, operating margin, and revenue contribution to parent BLU	

as a cognitive and behavioral driver, BMI as the pathway for value reconfiguration, and AI readiness as an enabler or moderator of the EM–BMI relationship. The four propositions (P1–P4) offer a theoretically grounded account of how BLUs can build innovation and adaptive capacity under fiscal and technological challenges, extending corporate entrepreneurship and dynamic capabilities into the public sector context.

As a conceptual framework, this paper does not provide empirical validation of the proposed relationships. The reliance on secondary literature means that causal mechanisms are inferred theoretically, without direct evidence from the Indonesian BLU context. Furthermore, while the model emphasizes EM, BMI, and AI readiness, other contextual factors—such as regulatory frameworks, institutional pressures, leadership styles, or organizational culture—may also significantly influence financial performance in hybrid organizations. Finally, the framework is developed in the Indonesian BLU setting, which may limit its direct applicability to other public service models without contextual adaptation.

In addition to its theoretical contribution, the framework offers implications at multiple levels. BLU business units should cultivate an entrepreneurial mindset and AI readiness to drive business model innovation, while parent BLUs must provide governance and strategic alignment. Line ministries should reduce bureaucratic barriers, foster cross-sector collaboration, and embed AI-driven transformation into sectoral planning. At the fiscal policy level, the Ministry of Finance can introduce incentives and adaptive regulation to balance autonomy with accountability. Together, these measures enable BLUs to achieve financial performance while fulfilling their dual mandate of generating revenue and creating public value.

Future studies should empirically validate the framework through large-scale surveys and SEM–PLS, while longitudinal designs could capture the dynamics of innovation adoption and strategic renewal in BLUs. Comparative research across sectors (e.g., education vs. healthcare) or countries with similar hybrid models would enhance generalizability. Further work may also examine how institutional pressures, digital governance, and leadership styles interact with EM and AI readiness in shaping BMI. Such inquiries can refine the model and yield actionable insights to strengthen BLU’s financial sustainability and public value in a digital, resource-constrained environment.

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